

The Weave of My Life: A Dalit Woman's Memoirs: *A Study in Subaltern Vision*

Bojja Pranathi Shubhasri

Research Scholar (Ph.D)

Department of English

Osmania University

Abstract

This article explores the powerful narrative of a Dalit woman's life, highlighting the intricate interplay of personal and socio-political experiences. This article delves into how the memoirs reflect the subaltern perspective, revealing the marginalized voice of a Dalit woman navigating a society marked by caste discrimination and systemic inequities. By analysing the memoirs through the lens of subaltern studies, the article seeks to uncover the nuanced ways in which personal identity and collective struggle are woven into the fabric of social resistance. This study offers insights into the broader implications of Dalit literature and its role in challenging dominant narratives, contributing to a deeper understanding of resistance and empowerment within marginalized communities.

Keywords: Dalit woman, socio-political experiences, social resistance, subaltern, dalit literature, marginalized communities etc.

Introduction

The emergence of Dalit self-awareness can be traced to Marathi literature of the 1970s in India. As one commentator notes, "The established literature of India is Hindu literature. But it is Dalit literature, which has the revolutionary power to accept new science and technology and bring about a total transformation. 'Dalit' is the name for total revolution; it is revolution incarnate." This statement underscores the transformative potential of Dalit literature, especially the autobiographies of Dalit writers, which are highly popular in Marathi and illustrate that reality can be more astonishing than fiction. Works such as Omprakash Valmiki's *Joothan* (1985) and Namdev Dhasal's poetry have significantly influenced writers in neighboring states like Karnataka, Tamil Nadu, and Andhra Pradesh. Today, Dalit literature has achieved pan-Indian recognition. Daya Pawar's *Baluta*, the first Dalit autobiography, has been followed by others like Bama's *Karukku* (Tamil) and Siddhalingaiah's *Uru Keri* (Kannada).

Urmila Pawar's *The Weave of My Life: A Dalit Woman's Memoirs* stands out as a rare example of autobiography in Indian literature, which tends to favour poetry and fiction. This memoir addresses major issues of class, caste, and gender in the Indian context, highlighting the dual oppression of Dalit women based on both caste and gender. Besides documenting a woman's journey to selfhood and her struggle with poverty, caste barriers, and patriarchy, it provides a broader view of Indian (especially Maharashtrian) culture, including inter-personal and inter-communal relations, conflicts, and tolerances.

"Weaving" serves as the central metaphor in this memoir. The protagonist's mother's weaving of bamboo baskets symbolizes their low caste status and severe economic poverty. On a deeper level, it also represents the connections between human lives on various levels. As the author states, "My mother used to weave aaydans. I find that her act of weaving and my act of writing are originally linked. The weave is similar. It is the weave of pain, suffering, and agony that links us." Urmila, the protagonist, is born into a very poor Mahar caste family in a village near Ratnagiri. Due to extreme poverty, the women in her village must venture into the nearby woods to gather firewood and sell it in Ratnagiri, contending with numerous geographical hazards along the way. Their struggle for basic survival leads them to curse their ancestors for choosing that village as their permanent home.

Women from our village made the arduous journey to the market in Ratnagiri to sell various goods. They carried heavy bundles on their heads filled with firewood, grass, rice, semolina, long pieces of bamboo, baskets, or mangoes, their loads so heavy that they risked injury. They would set out early in the morning, navigating a difficult road that wound up and down the hills between the village and Ratnagiri. The trip was exhausting.

As they approached the first hill, the frustrated women would voice their grievances with fervent curses, targeting the ancestral patriarch who, if he had been alive to hear them, would have been cursed anew. Their ire was directed at him for choosing the remote village of Phansawale, situated in a difficult and inconvenient terrain, nestled in a secluded part of the hills. They would lament,

"May his dead body rot... why did he have to come and stay here, in this godforsaken place?" "May his face burn in the stove!" "Was he blind or what? Couldn't he see this

wretched land for himself?” “Didn’t he notice these treacherous hills, paths, and forests? I wish someone had slapped him for making this decision!”

My mother was among those women who voiced their curses. We heard countless expletives from her! (Pp.2-3.)

The issue of poverty is intricately connected to her Dalit identity as a Mahar, which is one of the lowest castes in the Hindu varna hierarchy, as well as the challenges of being a woman in a patriarchal Indian society. Throughout her life, she struggles against these adversities to assert her selfhood and achieve fulfillment. The narrator, like many in her community, faces economic hardship. Their poverty deprives them of adequate food, clothing, proper shelter, and other basic comforts. This is vividly illustrated in her description of their eating habits and the extent of their poverty:

They managed to buy a small amount of rice, which they cooked in a large mud pot and served with a thin, watery soup. The men were served first, eating from a single communal dish. They sat on their haunches to eat, as if they were sitting down to defecate. Although it was true that Dalits had a tradition of sharing food from one plate, this was often due to the scarcity of plates in their homes. (P.17.)

Due to their extreme poverty, people in her community often resort to begging for festive food from upper-caste families:

“Our sisters-in-law, Vitha and Parvati, would also beg along with other women in our community... Their entire household would survive on those leftovers for two days. In some households, the flesh of dead animals would be consumed, but that was forbidden in ours” (P.43).

Similarly, their economic hardships prevented them from having adequate clothing:

“I had only two sets of clothes, which I wore alternately for three or four days. It was no surprise that they looked extremely dirty. My clothes made Biwalkar teacher froth at the mouth” (P.73).

Urmila Pawar describes her dual oppression, or double marginalization, through her experiences with gender and caste, which resulted in significant economic, social, and gender-based disadvantages in her life.

We were from the Mahad-Rajaput belt in the central Konkan region, which is notably backward compared to the north-south belt. I was born into a backward caste in a backward area, and as a girl, my situation was even more challenging. With Father passing away when we were young, Aaye had to be extremely frugal to manage. Essentially, she was a natural miser. There's a Marathi saying about a monkey drinking wine, becoming intoxicated, getting bitten by a scorpion, and then being cursed by a ghost—illustrating how people's inherent traits can amplify and lead to trouble. In our case, food was always scarce at home. (P.79.)

In addition to their economic hardships, her people endured social disabilities due to their untouchable caste. For instance, during the preparations for the Holi festival, the Mahars were assigned the most strenuous manual labor but were then conveniently ignored once their work was done. The Mahars were honoured with the task of delivering the first blow to the tree. Carrying the enormous trees down the hills to the Shambhu Temple in the village was an arduous job that would make people froth at the mouth. Once the trees were placed in front of the temple for the Holi celebration, members of the Maratha, Bhandari, and Kulwadi castes would merely touch the tree ceremonially. However, the real labour fell to the Mahars, who had to lift the heavy trunks and set them up. Despite their crucial role, the Mahars were ignored during the actual Holi rituals and celebrations, with no place afforded to them in the festivities.

At dusk, the Marathas, Bhandaris, and Kulwadis would worship the Holi and set the trees ablaze. Following this, they would begin to pray loudly in a ceremony known as garhane, which involved numerous prayers for the village's prosperity and protection from calamities. Ironically, they also prayed for misfortunes to befall the Mahars. The ritual included howling and cursing, with harsh invective directed at the Mahars, who dared not protest. During the festivities, each man from the upper castes would carry the palanquin and dance until exhausted, while the Mahars were excluded from even touching it. (Pp.39-40.)

The author documents numerous instances of the cruelty endured by the Mahar people at the hands of upper-caste Hindus. One such example, which deeply unsettles rational and sensitive individuals, is as follows:

Once, while staying with Akka, I witnessed a distressing scene involving a poor couple from the village of Anaav. They were sitting on their haunches in the verandah. The husband, wrapped in a loincloth, had a large, gaping wound on his bare back. His wife sat beside him, crying and wiping her tears with her torn sari. In their village, there was a ritual where an upper-caste man inflicted a wound on a Mahar's back, and the Mahar's wife had to cover the wound with cloth and walk around, howling. This ritual, resembling some ancient sacrificial rites, treated the Mahar as a symbol of the sacrificed animal.

Dada, Akka's husband, advised them to resist this custom, calling it a symbol of outdated sacrificial practices. He urged them to consider conversion as a means to end such practices. At the time, I did not fully grasp his words, but now their significance is clear. Later, Akka remarked, "How are these people any different from our patients in the mental hospital?" (P.72.)

Urmila endures constant humiliation due to her caste in all her social interactions. When people learn of her Mahar caste, they often avoid her or display disdain, revealing their puritanical and separatist attitudes. On one occasion, when celebrating her younger daughter Manini's birthday, Manini invites her friend Kishore to share the birthday cake. Urmila is acutely aware of her Mahar caste, particularly before her conversion to Buddhism, and feels the sting of insult from the invitees.

Kishore and his brother came, enjoyed the cake, and left after the birthday celebration. The following day, Kishore's mother came to our door. Without entering, she began to abuse us. "We didn't realize you belonged to this caste when I sent my children here. From now on, don't offer my daughter anything to eat if she visits your house. We are Marathas and cannot eat with you." She left before I could respond. (P.202)

In addition to her lower-caste status, the crushing poverty prevents them from eating well, dressing properly, or maintaining cleanliness in public like others. Their basic human dreams are stifled by extreme poverty and caste discrimination. Urmila has therefore had to

struggle intensely against these hostile forces to forge her identity and overcome her feelings of humiliation and inferiority.

She starts her memoirs with a brief mention of her mother's marriage to her father, reflecting on their profession and characteristics:

My father was a man with many qualities. He had lost his first wife and wished to remarry. He agreed to marry my mother because she could weave cane baskets. However, my maternal grandfather, who was my mother's father, rejected him because he was a bijwar, meaning he was marrying a second time. He was also dark and less attractive compared to his daughter, who was fair and beautiful. Additionally, he was shorter than her. Even if these issues could be overlooked, his background was problematic: he had been educated in a school for converts and taught in one on Sinal Hill. Furthermore, my father's home was in a distant, obscure village far from the sea, whereas my mother's family lived right by the seashore. My mother's father said, "My daughter eats fresh fish from the sea every day, but this man can only provide dried fish! I will not give him my daughter!" Despite these objections, my mother's elder brother Vithu, who was a soldier, intervened, and eventually, the marriage took place (P.14).

She notes that her parents were stingy by nature, and her father served as a priest for their community. Even as a schoolgirl, she showed a deep interest in art and theatre, earning praise from her teachers. Due to their severe poverty, she observed that she couldn't enjoy the tasty and expensive food or have the adequate clothing that upper-caste people had. Alongside these dire economic conditions, she faced the harsh and humiliating caste discrimination practiced by Hindus. The death of Dr. B.R. Ambedkar at that time heightened her awareness of the Ambedkar Movement and the necessity of converting to Buddhism as a means to escape the humiliation of her Dalit condition.

It was these people who brought the news of Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar's death to us. They had heard it on the radio. That day is etched in my memory. It was evening, and I had come home limping after spraining my ankle at school. When I reached home, I was met with a strange sight: everyone in the house was weeping. I joined in the mourning, moved by their sorrow. Later, Nathuram announced he would travel to

Mumbai the next day for Babasaheb's final darshan and left. Gradually, I learned who Babasaheb was, and then the conversion happened almost suddenly.

Crowds from surrounding villages converged on the grounds of Gogate College in Ratnagiri, creating a sea of humanity. We also went, along with Govindadada and other villagers. Instructions were broadcasted from loudspeakers overhead, and the chanting of "Buddham Saranam Gachchami" resonated through the crowd, which we joined.

After the ceremony, we returned home. Govindadada and the villagers collected the idols and pictures of gods and goddesses from our walls, which Aaye used to worship daily, and threw them into a basket.

Post-conversion, Govindadada replaced the idols with a portrait of Dr. Ambedkar and a Buddha idol in the space previously occupied by the gods. Daily prayers ceased. Activists from our wadi went door to door teaching people the Buddha Vandana, the invocation to the Buddha. Our community, now with the belief that all comforts would come automatically, stopped praying to the gods for comfort. The activists organized the Buddha Vandana each evening. This was a new experience for us, leading to confusion as we tried to sing it. The tune went awry, words were misplaced, and lines were mixed up, causing us to laugh heartily. But gradually, we all learned it well. (Pp. 92-93.).

She marries Harishchandra according to Buddhist conventions, rather than the Hindu ones previously followed. After spending the first night with her husband, her mother-in-law confirms her virginity by referring to the evidence of bleeding. Urmila's frank and honest portrayal of her first sexual experience with her husband, a topic often avoided by Indian women writers, is both commendable and significant. In the Indian context, many female writers tend to remain silent about such intimate and gender-specific experiences, opting instead to discuss other aspects of life in a more sanitized manner. In contrast, Urmila Pawar's candid expression of her private experience challenges traditional boundaries of women's writing, pushing it beyond the constraints and rigidities typically observed. After his examination was complete, he came to the cot and suddenly threw his arms around me.

"The light... the light..." I managed to mutter as I got up from the bed.

“Never mind!” My husband’s hands were all over me, and I felt completely disoriented. I was overwhelmed by his touch and could sense his deep disappointment.

“So frigid!” he said the next morning. That was the judgment I received from him after our first night together. Yet, he seemed to smile to himself, perhaps expecting me to be “frigid” as evidence of my virginity. If I had taken any initiative, he might have suspected my virginity. I was far from frigid—I understood everything that was happening, but these actions were being imposed upon me against my wishes.

The next morning, I was shocked to find myself bleeding. My periods were regular, so I was confused about how this could have happened.

I asked my husband, who was idly strolling behind me in the verandah. “Aho, how did this happen?” He gave me a sharp tap on the head and said, “You idiot, don’t you understand? Let’s go inside; I’ll tell Aai. The first time is always like this.” He wasn’t really scolding me; he was laughing. It was yet another proof of my virginity, though this may not be the case for all women. (P.154.)

Over time, she has a son, Mandar, and two daughters, Malavika and Manini. Despite the demands of her family, she persists in her education, completing both her B.A. and M.A. from the University of Mumbai. However, when she expresses her desire to pursue an M.A., her husband disapproves. He questions her, “Why do you want to do M.A? Now pay more attention to the children and the house” (P.202.). Nevertheless, she is determined to continue her higher education in her spare time and reassures him that he need not worry about it.

Harishchandra strongly disagreed with her plans. He firmly believed that managing the household was solely a woman's responsibility and maintained that a man had the right to act however he wished. This perspective infuriated her and led to ongoing conflicts between them (202.).

Despite the patriarchal constraints on her pursuit of higher education, she persists and earns an M.A. degree from Mumbai University. Education, undoubtedly, liberates individuals from ignorance and helplessness. For her, it becomes a source of strength and courage, enabling her to confront life's challenges and assert her identity, ultimately leading to the happiness she seeks.

After completing her education, she secures a job to contribute to the family's income, complementing her husband's earnings. During this period, she actively engages in the Dalit Women's Organization and the Ambedkar Movement, driven by her new vision for women's rights. Her involvement in the women's organization leads to inevitable conflicts with her husband, who struggles to accept her transformation from a state of obedience and submission to one of independent thought and action.

He was bewildered by the sudden change in his wife's behaviour. Previously compliant and predictable, she now seemed entirely different, leaving him deeply confused. He felt he was losing control and sought to reassert his authority with greater force. What he didn't realize was that her horizons had expanded significantly; she had encountered the broader world and was no longer confined to the narrow boundaries of home.

Her mind was also in a state of flux. She was filled with new ideas, believing that women, like men, were individuals entitled to their own rights. She recognized that while men possessed physical strength, women had the power to give birth, capacities that should be valued differently rather than judged by the same standard. At the same time, her community challenged her, questioning her associations with women from other castes and implying that she was aligning herself with undesirable elements. Their disapproval made her feel as if she had joined a criminal faction. Nevertheless, she had gained a new perspective on women and had lost her fear. The women's movement had empowered her to view every person as an equal individual and to interact without prejudice. Pp.207-8)

This demonstrates how Urmila's experiences, knowledge, and vision have expanded well beyond the limits of narrow thinking and parochialism.

Occasionally, her husband oscillates between Buddhist and Hindu traditions. Although they were married according to Buddhist customs and he initially questions the significance of external symbols like the mangalsutra, he quickly reverses his stance. He reprimands her for removing the mangalsutra, showing a clear contradiction in his behaviour. Urmila reflects on this inconsistency in his views and actions.

Eventually, Harishchandra began to adopt similar views. At times, he questioned the significance of traditional symbols, asking, "Why do you need these surface symbols?"

What's so important about the black beads? What difference does it make if a married woman doesn't wear them?" However, this understanding would often give way to frustration. He would react with comments like, "Why would you wear a mangalsutra? Are you just waiting for me to die?" Occasionally, he would even refuse to accompany her, saying with a hint of satisfaction, "You're a feminist! Why do you need the company of a man?" Despite these outbursts, Urmila continued to pursue her activities and responsibilities as she wished, though it wasn't always easy. (P.212.)

Urmila develops a profound interest in Dalit literature and women's literature, engaging in creative writing that bolsters her subaltern activism. She writes with intense dedication, despite lacking a personal space for her work. This mirrors Virginia Woolf's observation on the challenges faced by women writers:

"But for women, I thought, looking at the empty shelves, these difficulties were infinitely more formidable. In the first place, to have a room of her own, let alone a quiet room or a sound-proof room, was out of the question, unless her parents were exceptionally rich or very noble, even up to the beginning of the nineteenth century." Urmila Pawar manages to overcome these fundamental obstacles, pursuing her writing career with remarkable determination. She takes pride in her achievement of having her stories published in the Dipavali magazines.

My stories were published in the Diwali issues of a few rather ordinary, disposable magazines. Despite their lackluster quality, my joy was boundless. I proudly shared the news of my stories in print with my office friends. "We can't even write a few sentences, but look at her! She's written so much, and it's actually printed!" Their amazement felt like a reward in itself.

I wrote everywhere: in the office, on the bus or train, at bus stops, and even while standing in queues. I scribbled furiously. Sometimes, the reactions were quite amusing. For instance, when I started writing with a ticket in hand, the person next to me would often try to peek at my work. Men would sometimes misinterpret this as a flirtatious gesture and lean closer, which would disturb me. However, my hasty handwriting and the vehicle's movement made it unreadable, causing them to eventually give up and

return to their own space. Occasionally, I'd miss my stop and have to walk back, sometimes even paying a fine to the ticket collector.

At night, after meeting everyone's needs, including my own, I would finally sit down to write undisturbed. I'd choose the kitchen to avoid bothering others and write quietly. Exhausted from the day, my eyes would droop with sleep, and I'd find myself dozing off. I'd shake myself awake, scold myself for being lazy, and push on, urging myself, "Wake up! How dare you sleep! Keep writing!" (Pp.190-91)

Despite her husband's concerns about her health, Urmila continued writing late into the night. This was the reality of a housewife who aspired to be a writer.

Her stories gained recognition and were translated into various Indian languages, earning her numerous awards. One of her stories was even adapted into a television play, establishing her as a prominent Dalit woman writer. Just as she was celebrating her achievements as an activist and a writer, she faced three devastating blows: the suicide of her son Mandar, the death of her husband from liver cancer, and the loss of her classmate Sugandha. During her husband's illness and subsequent death, Urmila endured criticism from her relatives, who disapproved of her unconventional behaviour, which conflicted with their caste norms and patriarchal expectations.

In the final days of Harishchandra's life, I was squarely blamed for his illness. Initially, it was claimed that his heartbreak over our daughter's rebellious marriage had led to his condition. Over time, my education, my job, my writing, my social work, my meetings, my programs, and even my very existence were blamed for his sickness. Yet, by then, nothing could affect me anymore. (265.)

She refuses to remove her mangalsutra (marital necklace of black beads) after her husband's death, defying the conventions of patriarchal society. Having grown hardened and mature, she faces her life with stoic resolve. Her journey is marked by a notable evolution: from innocence to experience, from inferiority to self-confidence, and from passivity to activism. What stands out in her character is her courage to assert herself while remaining within the traditional framework of patriarchy. Unlike some modern feminists who may justify or glorify pre- and post-marital affairs as part of their self-assertion, Urmila Pawar maintains her belief in the sanctity of chastity, never engaging in extramarital relationships.

Though Urmila Pawar's memoirs focus on her personal evolution, they also provide a detailed portrayal of many individuals she encountered, such as Meenakshi, Vasantrao Moon, and Eleanor Zelliot. While her story is personal, her memoirs serve as an invaluable cultural record of Dalits in Maharashtra. They offer a rich depiction of their unique dress codes, eating habits, joint family conduct, rites, rituals, entertainment, and dialects, contrasting sharply with those of Hindu Brahmanical traditions. As she concludes her memoirs, she asserts,

“I expect nothing from the readers. I want them to see that each and every person’s life is a social document” (268).

Written in a realistic fictional mode, Urmila Pawar’s memoir is distinguished by its honest, frank, and bold portrayal of a Dalit woman’s experiences, drawing comparisons to Afro-American women's narratives. The memoir does not shy away from revealing any harsh truths about her personal, domestic, and societal life, which is deeply admirable. It demonstrates that she, a subaltern woman from the lowest Mahar caste, can assert her voice and express her individual and social vision through writing. The authenticity and honesty of her narrative are highly commendable.

The memoir is an odyssey of self-discovery, chronicling her spiritual journey from ignorance to knowledge, from helplessness to courage, from diffidence to confidence, and from multiple bondages to emancipation within the patriarchal framework. It serves as a form of scripto-therapy, providing her with a sense of relief and catharsis. This self-narrative not only helps her unburden her heart but also acts as a “prod to self-understanding, self-improvement, and self-healing” for the reader. It underscores that Urmila Pawar’s life, like every woman's life, is unique.

The English translation by Maya Pandit effectively captures the ethnic essence of the original Marathi text. Columbia University Press has commendably edited the memoir to suit an international audience. However, despite the thorough editorial process, a few typographical errors have occurred. For instance, Malavika is mistakenly spelled as ‘Malakiva’ in the section of family photographs after page 170. The inclusion of photographs of the protagonist and her family enhances the significance of the work. Additionally, the annotated notes and glossary of culture-specific terms are valuable in helping non-Marathi and non-Indian readers understand the text more clearly.

References:

1. Bagul, Baburao. "Dalit Literature is but Human Literature," *Journal of Literature & Aesthetics*, Vol: 8, Nos: 1& 2. Jan-Dec 2008. Ed. S. Sreenivasan, Kollam (Kerala) P.28.
2. Pawar, Urmila. *The Weave of My Life: A Dalit Woman's Memoirs*. Tr. Maya Pandit. New York: Colombia University Press. 2009. P. ix. (All the page references are to this edition.) Print.
3. Woolf, Virginia. *A Room of One's Own*, New Delhi: UBSPD Publishers' Distributors, 1999. P. 50. Print.
4. Henke, Suzette. *Shattered Subjects: Trauma and Testimony in Women's Life-Writing*. New York: St. Martin's Press, 1998, P.25. Print.
5. Smith, Sidonie, and Julia Watson, *Reading Autobiography: A Guide for Interpreting Life Narratives*. Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press, 2001. Pp. 22-23. Print.
6. Heilbrun, Caroline. *Writing a Woman's Life*. New York: Baltimore Books, 1988. P.35. Print.